

×*Draviera*: Valid Publication of a Nothogeneric Name for Hybrids Between *Dracaena* and *Sansevieria* (Asparagaceae)

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Abstract—The nothogeneric name ×*Draviera* is proposed for hybrids between *Dracaena* and *Sansevieria*.

Dracaena Vand., as traditionally circumscribed, is paraphyletic in regards to *Sansevieria* Thunb. (Lu *et al.* 2014; Takawira-Nyenya *et al.* 2018) Takawira-Nyenya *et al.* (2018) consequently subsumed *Sansevieria* into *Dracaena*. This change has not yet found its way to the general public, which will likely hold on to the familiar *Sansevieria* for decades to come.

The only intergeneric hybrid between *Dracaena* and *Sansevieria* known to me is a purported cross between *Sansevieria parva* N.E.Br. (\equiv *Dracaena parva* (N.E.Br.) Byng & Christenh.) and *Dracaena surculosa* Lindl. (as *Dracaena godseffiana* hort.) patented in 2016 under the name ‘SUDRASAN01’ (Suphachadiwong 2016). This cultivar is likely identical to the plant recently brought on the market in the Netherlands as *Draviera* FIREFLIES.

To my knowledge, the nothogeneric name *Draviera* has not been validly published, which is why I propose it here:

×*Draviera* anon. ex M.van der Meer **nothogen. nov.**
= *Dracaena* Vand. × *Sansevieria* Thunb.

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×*Draviera* 'SUDRASAN01'
(reproduced from Suphachadiwong 2016)

×*Draviera* FIREFLIES
at garden center GroenRijk de Wilskracht in The Hague, the Netherlands

Literature

Lu, P., & Morden, C. (2014). Phylogenetic Relationships among Dracaenoid Genera (Asparagaceae: Nolinoideae) Inferred from Chloroplast DNA Loci. *Systematic Botany*, 39(1): 90-104. <https://doi.org/10.1600/036364414x678035>

Suphachadiwong, T. (2016). *Sansevieria*×*Dracaena* plant named ‘SUDRASAN01’. USPP26912P3. <https://patents.google.com/patent/USPP26912>

Takawira-Nyenywa, R., Mucina, L., Cardinal-McTeague, W. & Thiele, K. (2018). *Sansevieria* (Asparagaceae, Nolinoideae) is a herbaceous clade within *Dracaena*: inference from non-coding plastid and nuclear DNA sequence data. *Phytotaxa*, 376(6): 254-276. <https://doi.org/10.11646/phytotaxa.376.6.2>